

1-Aryl substituted-3-(2'-chlorophenyl)-5-(3''-phenyl-4''-oxo-(3''H)-quinazolin-2''-mercaptoacetyl)formazans as insecticidal agents

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Abstract : Synthesis of some novel formazans have been carried out by the reaction of 2-mercapto-2-(methylamido-2'-chloro-*N*-benzylidene)-3-phenyl-4-oxo-(3*H*)-quinazoline with diazotised solution of aromatic amines in pyridine and screened for their insecticidal activity against *Tribolium confusum*.

Keywords : Formazans, insecticidal activity, *Tribolium confusum*.

Introduction

The biological utility of formazans for staining tissues and visualization of reducing enzymes in normal neoplastic tissues are known for a long time¹. Antiviral and antibacterial activities of a number of formazan derivatives have also been reported². Quinazolinones also have immense biological importance³.

The present communication hence reports the synthesis of some new formazans incorporated with this nucleus and their insecticidal activity against jawar grains infected with *Tribolium confusum*, which is a serious pest of rice and milled products⁴.

Results and discussion

The substituted ester-2-mercapto-(3-phenyl-4-oxo-(3*H*)-quinazolin)-ethyl acetate (**2**) was synthesized from 2-mercapto-3-phenyl-quinazolin-4-one (**1**) by treating with ethyl chloroacetate. Its IR spectrum showed two distinct vibrations at 1756 cm⁻¹ and at 1670 cm⁻¹ respectively. These were characterized as carbonyl group stretching vibrations, the former being of an ester linkage while the latter was identified as that of the quinazoline ring system.

Subsequent hydrazinolysis gave 2-mercapto-(3-phenyl-4-oxo-(3*H*)-quinazolin)-acetic acid hydrazide (**3**). Absence of band at 1756 cm⁻¹ but a new vibration at 1635 cm⁻¹ was visible in its spectrum. This was the

carbonyl group vibration now being part of an amide linkage hence confirming the process of hydrazinolysis. The hydrazide was further reacted with *o*-chlorobenzaldehyde to yield compound **4** which was a substituted *N*-benzylidene derivative namely : 2-mercapto-2-(methylamido-2'-chloro-*N*-benzylidene)-3-phenyl-4-oxo-(3*H*)-quinazoline.

The IR spectrum showed a band at 1620 cm⁻¹ which indicated the presence of an N=C linkage. Treatment with diazotised solution of *p*-chloroaniline yielded the formazan 1-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-3-(2'-chlorophenyl)-5-(3''-phenyl-4''-oxo-(3''*H*)-quinazolin-2''-mercapto acetyl) formazan (**5a**). A lower frequency vibration at 1530 cm⁻¹ was observed in its IR spectrum which was of the azo linkage. The structure was further supported by NMR and mass spectrum. The characteristic feature in the NMR spectrum (in CH₃OD) of compound **3** was a singlet at δ 8.27 for the single proton of N=CH group which was absent in compound **4**.

The mass fragmentation pattern of **5a** (Scheme 2) gave the molecular ion peak at M⁺ 587 and the isotopic peak at 589 (M+2) and 591 (M+4) respectively, indicating the presence of two chlorine atoms in the molecule. Further fragmentation gave ion 'a' at *m/z* 447, 449 and 'b' at *m/z* 140, 142 by fission of the C-N bond. Fragment 'b' by loss of nitrogen yielded the chlorophenyl cation (**1**) at *m/z* 112, 114 respectively.

- 5a R = Cl, R' = R'' = H 5c R = R'' = H, R' = CH₃
 5b R = R'' = H, R' = NO₂ 5d R = NO₂, R' = H, R'' = CH₃

Scheme 1

Fragment 'a' on the other hand cleaved to form the amido substituted quinazolinone ion (c) which appeared at m/z 310 and the chloro substituted benzonitrile ion (d) at m/z 138, 140. The relative intensities of the fragments 'a', 'b', 'd' and '1' were approximately in the ratio of 1 : 3.

Ion (c) also underwent cleavage forming the methylene substituted quinazolinone fragment (e) by loss of amido

group at m/z 267. Subsequent loss of the methylene group gave the 3-phenyl substituted mercapto quinazolinone ion at m/z 253 (f) which by loss of the phenyl radical gave the base peak at m/z 176/77 i.e. ion (g). The ion further cleaved giving fragment at m/z 145 (h), 119 (i), 116 (k) and 90/91 (j) respectively.

The formation of the 2-mercapto-quinazolin-4-one ion as the base peak was in accordance to the earlier studies⁵.

Scheme 2

Mass fragmentation of 1-(p-chlorophenyl)-3-(2'-chlorophenyl)-5-(3''-phenyl-4''-oxo-(3''H)-quinazolin-2''-mercaptoacetyl)formazan

Insecticidal activity : The culture of *Tribolium confusum* was maintained in glass bakelite jars using standard medium of whole wheat flour supplemented with brewers' yeast at 30 ± 1 °C and 70 + 5% relative humidity following the reported procedure⁶. 5 g of the synthesized formazans were taken in 95 ml of benzene. This was considered as the stock solution. Three doses were made by serial dilution i.e. 1.0, 2.5 and 5.0 ml/100 g seeds

including control. Three replications were used to test the ability of the beetle to develop on broken jawar seeds treated with the compounds. Ten newly hatched larvae were carefully transferred to the cultured tubes containing 10 g of broken jawar seeds treated with different concentrations of the synthesized compounds. Observations were made on a period required for adult emergence, the number of insects survived and loss % grain weight.

To calculate the survivality of insects, the newly emerged beetles were counted till the emergence of the last adult and the emerged beetles were removed to prevent further breeding. The adult percentage mortality at a concentration of 1 ml/100 g of jawar grains ranged between 23.3% (5d) to 3.33% (5c). At a concentration of 2.5 ml/100 g, the percentage varied between 30% (5d) to 16.67% (5c). However at 5.0 ml/100 g, maximum activity of 46.67% was observed in 5b and least in 5c (30%) as compared to the control (0%). Analysis of adult emergence of *Tribolium confusum* showed a 50% emergence in 5b at 1 ml/100 g with a minimum of 23.3% in 5c. At 2.5 ml/100 g, the percentage of adult emergence increased to 56.67% and upto 30% in the same compounds 5b and 5c. With a further increase in the concentration i.e. 5 ml/100 g the percentage ranged between 60% (5b) to 36.67% (5c) as compared to the control (90%).

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was also performed to see the significance of treatment given and CD at 5% for each experiment was observed and found to be 4.62 for adult mortality and 4.99 for adult emergence.

This data hence revealed that all the doses were significant when compared to the control (Table 1).

Experimental

All the melting points were taken in an electrical 'Neolab' apparatus and are uncorrected. The IR spectra were recorded on Shimadzu 8101A spectrophotometer. NMR was carried out on Bruker DPX 300 MHz and DPX 400 MHz spectrophotometer in CH₃OD, while mass was recorded on a JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 instrument.

2-Mercapto-3-phenyl-quinazolin-4-one was prepared by reported method⁷.

2-Mercapto-(3-phenyl-4-oxo-(3H)-quinazolin)-ethyl acetate (2): Mixture of 2-mercapto-3-phenyl-quinazolin-4-one (0.01 mol), ethyl chloroacetate (0.02 mol) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (1 g) were refluxed in dry acetone (10 ml) for 6–8 h. On distilling off the excess solvent, the solution was poured into ice water. A solid separated out which was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol, yield 70%; m.p. 80 °C; IR(KBr) 2906, 3148

(-CH₂ stretching), 1756 (C=O, ester), 1670 (C=O), 1610 (C=N), 1250 (C=S); ¹H NMR (CH₃OD) δ 3.92 (2H, s, CH₂), 2.76 (2H, q, CH₂CH₃), 1.95 (3H, t, CH₂CH₃), 7.22–8.15 (9H, m, ArH).

Table 1. Adult mortality and adult emergence of *Tribolium confusum* on jawar seeds treated with formazans

Compd.	1.0 ml/100 g		2.5 ml/100 g		5.0 ml/100 g	
	X	Y	X	Y	X	Y
5a	10	40	20	46.67	40	56.67
5b	16.7	50	26.67	56.67	46.67	60
5c	3.33	23.3	16.67	30	30	36.67
5d	23.3	36.7	30	43.33	40	50
Control	0	90	0	90	0	90

X = Mean percentage : adult mortality.

Y = Mean percentage : adult emergence.

ANOVA

Source of variation	Adult mortality			Adult emergence		
	df	MS	f	df	MS	f
Chemical	3	402.78	24.17	3	1032.41	53.10
Concentration	2	2036.11	122.17	2	533.33	27.43
Chemical concentration	6	36.11	2.17	6	7.41	0.38
Error	24	16.67		24	19.44	
Total	35			35		
		SEM = 2.36			SEM = 2.56	
		CD at 5% = 4.62			CD at 5% = 4.99	

2-Mercapto-(3-phenyl-4-oxo-(3H)-quinazolin)-acetic acid hydrazide (3): Hydrazinolysis of 2 (0.01 mol) with 99% hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) in absolute ethanol (10 ml) was carried out under anhydrous conditions by refluxing for 14–15 h. The contents on cooling gave a solid which was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol, yield 65%; m.p. 100 °C; IR(KBr) 3315, 3420 (NH, NH₂), 1670 (C=O), 1635 (C=O, amido), 1250 (C=S); ¹H NMR (CH₃OD) δ 3.88 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.32–8.01 (9H, m, ArH), 8.59–9.01 (3H, m, NHNH₂).

2-Mercapto-2-(methylamido-2'-chloro-N-benzylidene)-3-phenyl-4-oxo-(3H)-quinazoline (4): o-Chlorobenzaldehyde (0.015 mol) and compound 3 (0.001

mol) were refluxed together in methanol (12 ml) containing 3–4 drops of glacial acetic acid for 3–4 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and the separated solid after filtration and drying was recrystallised from methanol, yield 75%; m.p. 55 °C; ¹H NMR (CH₃OD) δ 3.85 (2H, s, CH₂), 8.27 (1H, s, N=CH), 7.29–7.88 (13H, m, ArH), 9.54 (1H, s, CONH) (Found : C, 61.54; H, 3.81; N, 12.49. Calcd. for C₂₃H₁₇O₂N₄SCl : C, 61.53; H, 3.79; N, 12.48%).

1-(p-Chlorophenyl)-3-(2'-chlorophenyl)-5-(3''-phenyl-4''-oxo-(3''H)-quinazolin-2''-mercapto acetyl) formazan (5a) : *p*-Chloroaniline (0.015 mol) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (3 ml) and stirred with conc. HCl (2 ml) at 0 °C. A solution of sodium nitrite (0.69 g, 0.01 mol) in water (5 ml) was then added dropwise with constant shaking and maintaining the temperature below 0–5 °C. The diazotised solution was then added gradually with stirring to a solution of **4** (0.01 mol) in pyridine (15 ml). The reaction product was allowed to stand at room temperature overnight. It was then decomposed by pouring in ice cold water, filtered, washed thoroughly with cold water and recrystallised with petroleum ether (60–80 °C), yield 45%; m.p. 80 °C (Found : C, 59.36; H, 3.39; N, 14.31. Calcd. for C₂₉H₂₀N₆O₂SCl : C, 59.38; H, 3.40; N, 14.33%); IR (KBr) 1640 (C=O), 1620 (C=N), 1530 (N=N), 1510 (NO₂), 3200–3300 (-NH), 1250 (C=S), 640 (C–Cl); ¹H NMR (CH₃OD) δ 3.81 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.54–8.03 (13H, m, ArH), 9.23 (1H, s, CONH).

Mass : 587 (M⁺), 589 (M+2), 591 (M+4); *m/z* 449, 447, 310, 267, 253, 177 (100%), 145, 142, 140, 139, 138, 119, 116, 114, 112, 91.

Similarly the other formazans were prepared **5b**, yield 45%; m.p. 80 °C (Found : C, 58.21; H, 3.32; N, 16.39. Calcd. for C₂₉H₂₀N₇O₄SCl : C, 58.24; H, 3.34; N,

16.40%). **5c**, yield 45%; m.p. 75 °C; ¹H NMR (CH₃OD) δ 3.97 (2H, s, CH₂), 2.56 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.35–7.91 (13H, m, ArH), 9.37 (1H, s, COHN) (Found : C, 63.57; H, 4.08; N, 14.78. Calcd. for C₃₀H₂₃N₆O₂SCl : C, 63.54; H, 4.06; N, 14.82%). **5d**, yield 40%; m.p. 80 °C (Found : C, 60.21; H, 3.65; N, 14.06. Calcd. for C₃₀H₂₂N₆O₄SCl : C, 60.23; H, 3.68; N, 14.05%).

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